

Framing the Ukraine Conflict in Arab Media: Perception, Bias, and Challenges

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Editorial control over the allocation of airtime and space plays a crucial role in shaping political and social agendas. This article examines Arab media coverage of the Ukraine crisis, addressing a gap in the literature that has largely focused on Western media. Through content analysis, the study identifies the dominant themes in Arab media reporting on the conflict. The findings reveal that 'politics' received the highest level of attention (50%) across the selected outlets. Coverage of the 'humanitarian situation' ranked second (20%), followed by the 'military' (18.4%) and 'financial' (16.9%) aspects of the conflict. In contrast, categories such as 'sports politics,' 'other,' and 'difficult to determine' received minimal attention. Although humanitarian concerns constituted the second most frequently covered theme, the substantial disparity between the prominence of 'politics' and 'humanitarian issues' suggests that humanitarian aspects were not prioritized by the Arab media. The study highlights the need for media outlets to strive toward more balanced reporting that remains independent of personal opinions, biases, ideologies, or institutional agendas.

Keywords: Russia-Ukraine War, Humanitarian Situation, Humanitarian Coverage, Middle Eastern Media, First Reaction of Media

Introduction

This article investigates the coverage of the Ukraine conflict by Arab media, addressing a gap in the existing literature, which has predominantly focused on Western media

(Jumbert 2020; Bunce et al. 2019). Given the Arab region's own history of conflict and its extensive experience in reporting on wars, it provides a valuable perspective for understanding media portrayals of international crises. Historically, Ukraine remained under Moscow's influence following its independence in 1991, with tensions escalating during the Orange Revolution (2004–2005), President Yanukovich's refusal to join the European Union in 2013, and Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014 (Asemah-Ibrahim et al. 2022; Higgins 2014; Gorbach 2020). Moscow's backing of separatists in Donetsk and Luhansk, NATO disputes, and increasing border militarization culminated in an invasion of Ukraine on 24 February 2022 (Richter 2022). This invasion displaced millions of people (International Rescue Committee 2023) and caused thousands of civilian and military casualties (Statista 2023; Mediazona 2023; Vlahos 2023).

Scholars widely question whether mass media can offer fair and objective accounts of war (Nossek 2004; Thussu 2019; Dolgova 2020). Studies show that in times of conflict, media often act as instruments of "soft power," align with state narratives, and underreport civilian suffering (Barnett and Roselle 2008; Robinson 2004; Sharaf 2013). Reporting on Ukraine reflects this: Russian media frame the war as a "special military operation" (TASS 2022), while Ukrainian and Western media describe it as an "invasion" (Yen-My 2023). Research also highlights racial and cultural biases, with Western coverage portraying Ukrainian refugees as "civilized" in contrast to prior

depictions of Arab or African refugees (Iberi and Saddam 2022). Such disparities raise questions about embedded prejudices and the political objectives of news framing.

Given that most existing studies critically examine Western media practices, there is a pressing need to investigate non-Western contexts (Allen 2018; Chouliaraki 2008; Carpi 2020). This article addresses this gap by analysing Arab media coverage of the Ukraine crisis, focusing on the question: What are the dominant themes emerging from Arab media reporting? In addition to humanitarian reporting, it considers economic, military, and geopolitical dimensions, thereby providing an empirical contribution to scholarship on media, conflict, and humanitarianism beyond the Western paradigm.

Existing Debates on Ukraine Crisis

On February 24, 2022, the president of the Russian Federation Vladimir Putin issued an order for Russian forces to enter Ukraine, marking the beginning of the Ukraine crisis. Experts predicted it would be one of the most devastating wars in two centuries. The number of soldiers losing their lives surpasses the death toll in all recent conflicts and is rising daily (Poast 2022). Thousands have lost their lives and millions displaced, resulting in a humanitarian crisis (Ellerbeck 2023; Giordano 2022).

After the collapse of the USSR and emergence of the Russian Federation in 1991 (Miller 2017), Ukraine gained independence. However, Ukraine remains a topic of interest for Russia due to its large Russian-speaking population and security concerns (Qualls 2009). Kyiv was part of Russia until an armed conflict in the ninth century (Kuzio 2019), was later reclaimed under Catherine the Great in the eighteenth century, and Crimea was transferred to Ukraine in 1954 (Chatterjee 2014). After 1991, Moscow gained dominance in the “near abroad” (Tarique and Shaheen 2023).

Ukraine was one of Moscow’s satellite

states, with Russia exerting control over politics and business (Asemah Ibrahim et al. 2022). Tensions escalated after independence in 1991, notably during the “Orange Revolution” (Fengler et al. 2020). In 2013, Yanukovich’s rejection of the EU deal under Moscow’s pressure ignited conflict (Higgins 2014; Asemah Ibrahim et al. 2022). The annexation of Crimea in 2014 marked a turning point, with interference from global players complicating matters (Pifer 2017). Crimea was annexed after a staged referendum (Hansen 2015), and Moscow has since supported pro-Moscow groups in Luhansk and Donetsk (Gorbach 2020).

In 2021, Russia proposed draft agreements to prevent NATO expansion and troop deployments near its borders, demanding Georgia and Ukraine be excluded from NATO (Tarique and Shaheen 2023). When these demands were rejected, Russia built up troops along Ukraine’s border. Richter (2022) notes the West asked Russia to withdraw, but Moscow argued NATO’s presence threatened its security. On February 24, 2022, Russia invaded Ukraine from land, air, and sea. About 8 million Ukrainians fled (International Rescue Committee 2023). By August 2023, 9,369 people were dead and 16,646 injured (Statista 2023). Mediazona (2023) reported 28,652 Russian soldiers dead by July 2023, while Moscow admitted only 6,000 (Vlahos 2023). Tomlinson and Wehner (2023) note 20,000 Ukrainian soldiers lost their lives. The war left thousands stranded without basic necessities, endangered global trade, stunted growth, and caused worldwide fuel and food shortages.

The Ukraine Crisis and Its Economic Repercussions

As Clausewitz (1976) argued, war is an extension of politics by different means. The Ukraine crisis also involves economic dimensions, particularly Western sanctions on Russia and Moscow’s demand that adversary states pay for energy in Russian currency (Gelev and Popovska 2023).

Studies divide war's economic effects into two categories: "ruins of war" and "war renewal." The latter argues conflict can foster creativity and productivity (Benoit, 1973, 1978), while the former sees war as purely destructive (Kang and Meernik 2005). Financial crises can heighten a society's vulnerability to civil conflict (Chassang and Miquel 2009), and the economic costs of war have been extensively studied. Koubi (2005) demonstrated that both the intensity and timing of armed conflict influence economic growth, with prolonged wars occasionally fostering development in some contexts, though not in wealthier states. Kang and Meernik (2005) concluded that, overall, conflicts exert a negative impact on national economies, while Collier (1999) suggested that short wars may spur growth, in contrast to extended conflicts. Nordhaus (2002) estimated that the U.S. invasion of Iraq incurred a cost of approximately \$2 trillion. Employing a gravity model, Glick and Taylor (2010) found that armed conflicts substantially disrupt global trade. Similarly, Ganegodage and Rambaldi (2014) observed that Sri Lanka's civil war impeded economic growth despite high levels of investment.

The 2014 Ukraine Crisis also had major consequences. Bluszcz and Valente (2019) reported a 15.1% contraction in Ukraine's economy between 2013–2017, and Hoffmann and Neuenkirch (2017) noted falling stock returns in both countries. Liefert et al. (2019) showed sanctions raised food prices and reduced consumption but spurred Russian domestic production. Since 2014, the Ruble lost half its value against the dollar (Dreger et al. 2016). Russia's GDP also fell by 1% between 2014–2016 due to weak investment (Havlik 2014). While earlier studies assessed these impacts (Korovkin and Makarin 2021), there is limited literature on the ongoing 2022 full-scale war.

Sanctions as a tool to restrict global

market access have a long history, from the Napoleonic era to South African apartheid, Iraq, Iran, and Russia (Alexander 2009; Hufbauer et al. 2008; US Dept. of Treasury 2021). They are used during war to weaken an enemy or pre-emptively to avoid conflict. The Global Sanctions Database records 405 active sanctions, 300 of them in the last decade (Felbermayr et al. 2020). Most studies examine their impact on trade, investment, and GDP (Hufbauer and Oegg 2003; Kohl and Reesink 2019), as well as their effectiveness. Results are mixed: some show negative economic effects (Ahn and Ludema 2020), while others argue that sanctions often fail to achieve political goals (Shin et al. 2016).

The U.S. Magnitsky Act of 2012 introduced targeted sanctions against Russian officials, later expanded after Crimea's annexation in 2014 (Have 2020; Dreger et al. 2016). Russia faced sanctions in multiple waves from 2014–2017 (Bayramov et al. 2020), targeting elites involved in the annexation. These slowed growth, reduced business activity, and raised concerns among firms (Aalto and Forsberg 2016; Golikova and Kuznetsov 2017). Oil price drops worsened Russia's economy (Oxenstierna 2020), while firms sought new suppliers and financing (Abramova and Garanina 2018). Sanctions forced restructuring of supply chains (Scazzieri 2017) and harmed penalized firms' survival, assets, and jobs, especially in non-strategic industries (Ahn and Ludema 2020).

Despite warnings, Russia invaded Ukraine again in February 2022, triggering harsher sanctions. Many firms left Russia, yet the war continues. In 2019, EU–Russia energy trade exceeded €200 billion (Pisani-Ferry 2022). Sanctions drove global oil and gas prices up, hurting other economies. Scholars suggest diversifying suppliers and modernizing EU energy infrastructure (Khudaykulova et al. 2022). Russia faces mutual dependence, supplying only 8.4% of EU fossil fuels, but with limited market

alternatives (Edmond 2022).

Energy price shocks linked to geopolitical risks are well-documented. The 1990 Gulf War doubled oil prices (Mitsas et al. 2022; Antonakakis et al. 2017). Similarly, the 2022 invasion raised global energy costs, with sanctions on Russia reducing supply and pushing prices higher (Khudaykulova et al. 2022).

Reporting on the Ukraine Crisis

In today's interconnected world, the mass media play a crucial role in shaping perceptions of global conflicts, yet its ability to provide fair and objective reporting remains contested (Lippmann 1991; Thussu 2019; Curran et al. 2017). Scholars often argue that during wars, media become a tool of "soft power" rather than a neutral observer (Aday 2018; McQuail 2010). NATO's Strategic Communications Centre identifies three media roles in conflict: (1) adversarial observers striving for objectivity, (2) adversarial journalists taking sides, and (3) the media itself functioning as a symbolic battlefield (Szwed 2016). However, distinctions between these roles have blurred with the rise of digital and social media (Kwei 2022).

Research shows governments, particularly in the U.S., exert strong influence over wartime reporting (Rachlin 1988; Aday 2010). Journalists often align with national interests or succumb to nationalism (Henry 1981; Robinson 2004). Historical cases, such as Vietnam and Iraq, reveal how coverage emphasized military strength while downplaying civilian suffering (Hallin 1989; Sharaf 2013; Sakwa 2022). Media framing can escalate or de-escalate conflicts: constructive framing fosters peace, while adversarial coverage prolongs disputes (Lichtenstein et al. 2019).

The Russia–Ukraine war illustrates these dynamics. Western outlets often frame Russia as the aggressor, while Russian media portrays its invasion as a "special military operation" to secure national interests

(TASS 2022; Yen-My 2023). Chinese and Indian media emphasize diplomacy, economics, or nationalist concerns, often echoing Russian narratives (Hanley et al. 2023; Roy and Paul 2022). Studies highlight how global outlets like Reuters, AP, Xinhua, and TASS diverge in applying war vs. peace journalism frames (Yen-My 2023). Moreover, Russia deploys multichannel strategies—RT, Sputnik, think tanks, trolls, and bots—to spread disinformation and legitimize its actions (Chivvis 2017; Zhabotynska and Ryzhova 2022).

Overall, the literature demonstrates that wartime reporting is rarely neutral. Media often reflect geopolitical interests, frame conflicts selectively, and serve as an information battlefield alongside the physical one. Control over narratives—what is shown, omitted, or framed—can be as decisive as military victories (Hayward and Kearney 2023).

Contrasting Media Narratives

Since Russia's 2022 invasion of Ukraine, major news outlets have faced criticism for coverage that contrasts sharply with reporting on crises in Africa and the Arab region, raising charges of prejudice and racial bias (Witte 2022). CBS's Charlie D'Agata suggested Ukraine's crisis was unexpected because it occurred in a "civilized" country, while BBC's Ross Atkins appeared to condone remarks about "Europeans with blonde hair and blue eyes" being killed (Lawati and Ebrahim 2022; Al Jazeera 2022). Similarly, Al Jazeera's Peter Dobbie described Ukrainian refugees as "prosperous, middle-class people," implicitly contrasting them with African migrants (Carras 2022). Such cases underscore disparities in coverage: European conflicts are often portrayed with empathy and sophistication, whereas wars in Africa and the Arab region are framed in racialized or simplistic terms (Somerville 2017). These patterns reflect long-standing biases shaped by political agendas, cultural knowledge, and historical

legacies.

At the same time, media reporting in Ukraine and Russia has been shaped by government restrictions. In Moscow, the Kremlin banned terms like “war” and “invasion,” mandating euphemisms such as “special military operation” (CNN 2022). Russian state media echoed official justifications ranging from “de-Nazification” of Ukraine to NATO’s expansion threat and claims of historical entitlement, while minimizing battlefield losses (Thompson 2022; Mateo 2018).

Theoretical Framework

The notion of Media Social Responsibility has been extensively examined by scholars from multiple angles (Nordenstreng and Varis 1974; McQuail 1992; Shoemaker and Reese 1996; Curran and Seaton 2003; Wall 2010). This theory proposes the media’s fundamental journalistic ethical responsibility to act in the best interest of the masses and maintain objectivity and freedom of speech. The theory was coined by “The Hutchins Commission report” in 1947 which championed public well-being, by rendering precise, inclusive, and thorough news to the masses (Hutchins Commission 1947). The Media’s Social Responsibility theory came into being as a reaction to Libertarian theory that advocates a completely free media by suggesting that media should conform to journalistic ethical guidelines and self-govern in order to eliminate problems like fake news, subjectivity, and dramatization (Siebert, Peterson, and Schramm 1956). This notion has been furthered by prestigious academics such as Nordenstreng and Varis (1974) who highlight the universal side of Media Social Responsibility theory by underlining the significance of equal opportunity for information reach and fair depiction of all segments of the society. Moreover, Curran and Seaton (2003) argues that the media need to serve as a check on the power corridors and promote equitable public

dialogue. The media, according to Media

Social Responsibility theory, is also expected to underscore social problems and injustices (McQuail 2010). Concerning the fake news issue, Wall (2010) believes that Media Social Responsibility theory is more pertinent and relevant in the present age of digitalization than ever before. Wall argues that the media organizations should adhere to ethical guidelines in order to counter issues such as fake news and divisions in the societies. Since Media Social Responsibility theory promotes a balance among the freedom of media and transparency, it acts as a guiding principle for the media to adhere to its democratic responsibilities (Christians et al. 2009).

Methodology and Research Design

Content analysis is a systematic and objective method for examining media texts, visuals, and audiovisual materials (Neuendorf 2016). It involves trained coders identifying the presence or absence of specific themes or messages (Krippendorff 2013) and has been broadly defined as a formal system of drawing conclusions from observed content (Stempel et al. 2003). Weber (1990) similarly views it as a procedure for making valid inferences from texts. Key steps include defining the unit of analysis, sampling, constructing categories, developing a coding scheme, coder training, ensuring inter-coder reliability, analysing data, and reporting results (Singletary 1994; Neuendorf 2016). Reliability and validity are central: replicability ensures that applying the same procedures produces similar results (Krippendorff 1980; Holsti 1969), while validity ensures that coding reflects the intended meaning (Neuendorf 2017). Quantitative content analysis converts communication into numerical values to identify trends, regularities, and relationships through statistical methods (Riffe et al. 2005). Beyond positivist objectivity, scholars now stress *intersubjectivity*: agreement among researchers about coding decisions, promoting consistency across interpretations (Neuendorf 2017).

Reliability refers both to inter-coder consistency and intra-coder consistency over time (Hansen and Machin 2018). In single-researcher projects, “solitary coding” requires dual coding by the same scholar to ensure *intrasubjectivity*—consistency in one’s own coding across time (Boréus and Bergström 2017). Validity further includes internal validity (accurate causal relationships) and external validity (generalizability of findings), which depend on representative sampling (Lacy et al. 2015).

Sampling

This study investigates media coverage from the Arab region, selected due to its prolonged exposure to conflicts and the extensive experience of its media in reporting wars. Four middle-power countries, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Egypt, and Türkiye, were chosen, with middle-power status in international politics serving as the primary selection criterion. From these countries, the oldest English-language newspapers were selected: *Hürriyet Daily News* (Türkiye, est. 1961), *Arab News* (Saudi Arabia, est. 1975), *Gulf News* (UAE, est. 1978), and *The Egyptian Gazette* (Egypt, est. 1880). These outlets generally maintain a pro-government stance, rendering them suitable for examining state-aligned media discourses. All newspapers provide digital archives, from which a total of 1,411 news articles were retrieved using keywords such as “Ukraine war,” “Ukraine invasion,” “Ukraine Crisis,” and “Russia’s invasion of Ukraine,” covering the period from February 24 to December 30, 2022. Due to the large volume of data, the analysis was restricted to the first month of the conflict (February 24–March 24, 2022), when coverage across all outlets was most intensive.

During the first month of the crisis, the selected outlets published a total of 458 articles (see Table 2). To align with the objectives of this study, only hard

TABLE 1
First Year Total Number of Articles Published

Total Number of Articles Published in the First Year				
Outlet’s Names	Arab News	The Egyptian Gazette	Gulf News	Hürriyet Daily News
Total Articles	607	22	217	565
Total 1 411				

news articles were retained, while opinion pieces, live blogs, and feature articles were excluded. This filtering resulted in a dataset of 378 hard news articles: *Arab News* (n = 220), *Gulf News* (n = 81), *Hürriyet Daily News* (n = 64), and *The Egyptian Gazette* (n = 13). Given the disproportionately large number of articles from *Arab News*, *Gulf News*, and *Hürriyet Daily News*, a random sampling procedure using a skip-interval method was employed to reduce the dataset to a manageable size while preserving representativeness (Neuendorf 2017). Specifically, every 13th article was selected from *Arab News* (n = 19), every 6th from *Gulf News* (n = 18), and every 5th from *Hürriyet Daily News* (n = 16). All articles from *The Egyptian Gazette* (n = 13) were retained due to its smaller volume. In total, this process resulted in a final sample of 66 hard news articles for content analysis. The study unit of analysis was paragraphs as I followed Krippendorff’s (2004) suggestion to use smaller documenting units as opposed to larger sample units. I found 1,721 paragraphs in total.

While one article from each newspaper was selected as the unit of analysis, it operated on paragraphs of that particular article for data coding (Neuendorf, 2017). A total of 2,112 paragraphs were reviewed (Table 4). Unlike work studying whole articles, this is based on Krippendorff’s (2004)

TABLE 2
First Month Total Number of Articles Published

Total Number of Articles Published in the First Month				
Outlet’s Names	Arab News	The Egyptian Gazette	Gulf News	Hürriyet Daily News
Total Articles	261	21	91	85
Total 458				

TABLE 3
Total Articles of First Month after Applying the Skip Interval

Total Number of Articles in First Month after Applying the Skip Interval				
Outlet's Names	Arab News	The Egyptian Gazette	Gulf News	Hürriyet Daily News
Total Articles	19	13	18	16
Total 66				

advice to always go to smaller units, as larger ones are likely “too rich or too complex to be described reliably.” Paragraphs also give readers clear, concise stopping points, generally one or two lines, that indicate a change in topic or direction. So, analysing paragraphs help to better understand how topics such as politics, geopolitics, military or humanitarian matters get attention span. This strategy also speaks to a central concern of the analysis: What are the dominant themes emerging from Arab media reporting?

Results and Discussion

The conflict between Moscow and Kyiv warrants significant media attention, as it fulfills several criteria of “newsworthiness” outlined in Galtung and Ruge’s (1965) research on news values. To address the first research question, “What are the dominant themes emerging from Arab media reporting?”, this article employed a content analysis methodology.

Overall Editorial Focus of Selected Arab Media Organizations

In this context, the content analysis operationalized the recurring themes in media coverage of the ongoing Ukraine crisis, with particular attention to the well-being

TABLE 4
Total Number of Paragraphs

Total Number of Paragraphs					
Outlet's Names	Arab News	Haaretz	The Egyptian Gazette	Gulf News	Hürriyet Daily News
Total Paragraphs	447	391	142	662	470
Total 2 112					

of affected populations. Among the selected news outlets, the ‘political/geopolitical’ dimension of the crisis received the greatest emphasis, accounting for 50.0% of all hard news articles (see Table 5). This was followed by coverage of humanitarian issues, which constituted 20.4% of the reporting (see Table 5). Humanitarian

coverage is alarmingly low, therefore, this study suggests more extensive Humanitarian Media reporting as the human welfare should be the center point of media coverage during conflicts and natural disasters. Moreover, the ‘military’ and ‘economy’ categories have received relatively similar focus from the stated Arab media organizations. The ‘military’ category has received the third highest coverage, which is 18.4% overall and economy 16.9% (see Table 5). This has been followed by the ‘difficult to determine,’ ‘other,’ and ‘sports politics’ which have received 1.4%, 2.0%, and 1.2% overall attention respectively. The ‘two or more topics’ category has not been covered at all by all selected media organizations. Hence, the results of this study indicate that the humanitarian situation of the region was not the prime issue for the media outlets, although the second highest coverage was given to the humanitarian issue. There was a big gap between the amount of coverage received by the ‘politics’ and ‘humanitarian’ categories. These results question the initial hypothesis concerning the pervasiveness of associated economic problems, which have received limited attention.

Furthermore, the media plays a central role, as per McCombs and Shaw’s (1972) agenda-setting theory, in identifying the importance of some specific topics for the general public. The degree of viewers’ attention/ interest and the perceived significance of a problem or a story in the public eye is formed

by the extent of airtime or space it receives. Therefore, the control of the editorial team over the allocation of airtime significantly influences the political and social agendas. Hence, the more airtime, the more prominent the story gets in the public eye. This clearly highlights the importance of airtime or space a story gets in news media and the way it influences the social or public discourse. Moreover, this editorial control on airtime allocation also molds public perception and social discourse (Shoemaker and Vos 2009). Additionally, news that receives greater space in the print medium and airtime in the visual medium as compared to other news stories is considered more significant and these stories get the attention of interest groups, lawmakers, the public, and so forth (Dearing and Rogers 1996). “Fair and impartial media coverage, which provides equal representation to all sides of a dispute, can foster better understanding among different groups and facilitate efforts towards peace” (Fahim and Islam 2024). “By generating dialogue and presenting a unifying narrative that transcends differences, such coverage can contribute to peacebuilding initiatives” (Galtung 1996).

Overall Focus of Individual Media Outlets by Per-Category

This study endeavors to investigate the humanitarian coverage of the Ukraine Crisis by the Arab media as the Arab region is itself a war-torn area and the Arab media

have a good amount of experience in conflict coverage. When contrasting the experience of Arab media and journalists in covering conflicts with that of other non-Occidental media, it becomes evident that the Arab media possesses a greater wealth of hands-on experience in both conflicts and conflict coverage. Consequently, for this study, selecting Arab media as the focus was a more logical choice compared to other non-Occidental media outlets. Even though digital technologies have revolutionized the news industry, the mainstream media (print and electronic) remain significant. Additionally, people try to use both types of media during war and conflicts for a broader understanding (Omoera 2010) of the effect of war, their security, and ability to maneuver the crisis situation (Melki and Kozman 2021). Therefore, the news media can shape people’s opinions pertaining to a specific subject or situation such as war. Hence, the media remain a significant entity during conflicts. To achieve this, the media purposely highlight some aspects more and downplay others by utilizing frames with the purpose of influencing their audience to think about what they want them to think about the war (Shalvee and Sambhav 2020; Omoera and Nwaoboli 2023).

In the following, this article explains the coverage of the war by the stated outlets dividing it into categories.

The Humanitarian Category

Media are the main source of information for the majority of people when they want

TABLE 5
Overall Focus of the Arab Media Organizations by percentage (%)

	Humanitarian	Military	Economy	Politics Geopolitics	Sports Politics	Two or more Topics	Other	Difficult to Determine
Arab News	13.1	12.5	20.5	40.2			4.6	
Gulf News	18.2	14.1	19.1	56.3	3		1.2	2.8
Hürriyet Daily News	27	31	9.7	51			1	0.8
The Egyptian Gazette	32.3	15.4	18.3	47.8				1.4
Total	20.4	18.4	16.9	50.0	1.2		2.0	1.4

to know about faraway miseries and define certain contexts of humanitarian crises (Rozakou, 2020; Joye, 2012). Hence, the role of media is crucial when it comes to the portrayal of occurrences and the audience's perception of distant miseries (Zhang and Luther 2020). Furthermore, it is the media organizations that can make the faraway miseries significant or vice versa in the public eye by giving more airtime or space to the story/stories. Therefore, the media constitute an extremely crucial connection between the faraway miseries audience and faraway miseries. That is why the media cannot be overlooked by any means.

To start with, *The Egyptian Gazette* has given the highest coverage to the humanitarian side of the war (32.3%). However, this is closely followed by the amount of attention given to the humanitarian side of the war by the *Hürriyet Daily News* (27%) (see Table 6). It is important to note that the geographical proximity factor did not affect the focus of the outlet.

The concept of proximity is not limited to physical distance alone (Franks, 2006), as cultural, ideological, financial, and political proximity also play important roles. This is referred to as communitarianism and cosmopolitanism (Chouliaraki 2008). Although the geographical proximity of a media organization to the conflict does influence the intensity and tonality of their reporting, the ideological, financial, and political proximity of the media organ or the countries where the media organ is located significantly impact the media coverage. Furthermore, how the media cover faraway events is influenced by the location of the media organization, which can determine whether the coverage is communitarian or cosmopolitan.

Although, *Hürriyet Daily News* is geographically closer to the war region than *The Egyptian Gazette*, still *The Egyptian Gazette* has given more attention to the humanitarian side of the war. Furthermore, *Gulf News* and *Arab News* have given the

third and fourth highest coverage to the humanitarian side of the Ukraine Crisis, 18.2% and 13.1% respectively (see Table 6). These figures clearly show us the focus and attention of the Arab media as far as the Ukraine Crisis coverage is concerned. Moreover, the works in question also stress that even as mass media reporting brings conflicts and wars to the attention of the general population, mass media reporting “also defines what qualifies as a humanitarian crisis, an emergency, an atrocity, and so on” (Carpi 2020; Donini 2020; Kotilainen 2020; Rozakou 2020).

The Military Category

Recent research on how the media covers wars and crisis reveals that journalists frequently fail to uphold their journalistic norms, particularly if the war affects the state in which they are employed and further emphasize that the nation's foreign policy heavily influences the media's reporting (Ravi 2005; Tumber and Palmer 2004; Vukasovich and Dejanovic-Vukasovich 2016). Although state censorship and foreign policy directions of a state significantly affect the media coverage especially in the time of conflicts, financial and ideological aspects also shape the stance of the media. For ages, the news media and the media in general have been employed as a “soft power,” particularly during armed conflicts. Dolgova's (2023) work discusses how TV channels in different countries report international news differently based on their citizens' interests and foreign policy priorities.

Generally, conflicts and the military aspect of conflicts draw the media's attention and receive a considerable amount of coverage. Therefore, this article is also interested in analyzing the coverage of the Arab media in relation to the military side of the Ukraine Crisis. Again, *Hürriyet Daily News* has given more attention to the military aspect of the war as compared to other media outlets. *Hürriyet Daily News* has given 31% coverage

TABLE 6
Dominant Recurring Theme of all Five Media Outlets

	Arab News (%)	Gulf News (%)	Hürriyet Daily News (%)	The Egyptian Gazette (%)
Humanitarian	13.1	18.2	27	32.3
Military	12.5	14.1	31	15.4
Economy	20.5	19.1	9.7	18.3
Politics/Geopolitics	40.2	56.3	51	47.8
Sports Politics		3		
Two or more Topics				
Other	4.6	1.2	1	
Difficult to Determine		2.8	0.8	1.4
Total	408	762	568	164

to the military side of the war (see Table 6). It is followed by *The Egyptian Gazette* (15.4%), *Gulf News* (14.1%), and *Arab News* (12.5%) (see Table 6).

The Economy Category

Economics is an important aspect of all conflicts and wars. Therefore, the media pays significant attention to the economic side of the war. Four out of the four selected media outlets have paid almost a similar amount of attention to the Ukraine Crisis. *Arab News* has given 20.5% of coverage to the economic side of the war followed by the *Gulf News* (19.1%), and *The Egyptian Gazette* (18.3%). The results show that *Hürriyet Daily News* has paid the least attention to the economic side of the war.

The Politics/Geopolitics Category

An objective journalism (media coverage) can either help stop a conflict or accelerate it (Abiodun and Nwaoboli 2023). Moreover, the relationship between the media and the stakeholders of a war or conflict does not merely affect the media's role in the war but also greatly influences the international community's response depending on the framing of the war in the media and the airtime (space) they allocate to (Puddephatt 2006). This indicates that both the quantity and nature of news coverage greatly affect the reaction of the local and global news viewers and the stakeholders of the war. Furthermore, the media is usually

employed as a tool in wars for shaping public opinion or deceiving the enemy through false information during conflicts, as argued by Puddephatt (2006), who quoted the example of the media's role in the Yugoslavian war.

Politics is an integral and inseparable part of all kinds of conflicts and wars. Therefore, this article also endeavors to investigate the Arab media coverage of the political aspect of the Ukraine Crisis. The politics/geopolitics category has received the highest coverage among all other categories. This clearly indicates the slant and focus of the selected media outlets. Concerning the individual media outlets, *Gulf News* has given the highest coverage (56.3%), followed by the *Hürriyet Daily News* (51%) the second highest, and *The Egyptian Gazette* (47.8%) is the third highest. The lowest of all is the attention given by the *Arab News* (40.2%) (see table 6). These results vividly underline the amount of importance given to the political aspect of the war by the Saudi, Emirati, Egyptian, and Turkish media. All of the selected media outlets prioritized the politics of the conflict and gave scant attention to the humanitarian, economic, military, and other aspects of the war.

The degree of viewers' attention/interest and the perceived significance of a problem or a story in the public eye is formed by the extent of airtime it receives. Therefore, the control of the editorial team over the allocation of airtime significantly influences

the political and social agendas. In addition, the editorial control exercised over the allocation of airtime has a significant impact on shaping social discourse (Shoemaker and Vos 2009). It is also worth noting that stories that receive extensive coverage from the media are often perceived as more significant and, consequently, receive greater attention from various segments of society, including policymakers, interest groups, and the general public (Dearing and Rogers 1996).

Conclusion

The media play a central role in shaping public attention, as audience perceptions of importance are influenced by the airtime given to an issue (McCombs and Shaw, 1972). Consequently, editorial decisions on coverage significantly affect public, political, and governmental agendas. This article addresses this gap by analysing Arab media coverage of the Ukraine crisis, focusing on the question: What are the dominant themes emerging from Arab media reporting? Findings show that political/geopolitical aspects dominated coverage, while humanitarian issues ranked second, followed by military and economic themes. This indicates that humanitarian concerns were secondary, and economic issues received limited attention. These results underscore the challenge of objectivity in conflict reporting. This study is limited to the first year of the conflict but highlights the need for comparative research on non-Western media conflict coverage. Future work should also examine the implications of emerging technologies, such as AI-powered drones and digital war representations, which are reshaping media and military communication strategies.

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